

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Target configuration for coupled systems (ICON-ESM, ECMWF, EC-Earth, IPSL-CM)

Milestone M1.1

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Target configuration of the coupled systems for WP1:

Background:

ESiWACE1 could show that it is technically possible to run leading European models at global horizontal resolution up to 1 km. However, simulations were uncoupled, model output was minimal or switched off, and execution times were much too slow for operational use.

ESiWACE2 will be based on previous results and push resolution towards unprecedented levels for coupled simulations in production mode that show a performance that would allow operational weather and climate predictions (at least 1 SYPD) with realistic model output with a resolution that is as high as possible. Four coupled models have been chosen for this exercise. The model configurations that are developed within WP1 of ESiWACE2 will be ported to the European pre-exascale EuroHPC systems planned for 2021. The scaling behaviour of the models will be diagnosed and documented.

To achieve this goal towards Deliverable D1.1 and D1.3, this Milestone is specifying the model configurations that will be used for the four models that will be run in production mode. Three of the models are aiming for the model output requirements of the 2nd phase of the DYAMOND intercomparison to define a realistic model output for production simulations¹.

Model configurations:

EC-Earth:

We will use the coupled EC-Earth model which uses OpenIFS for the atmosphere, NEMO for the ocean and OASIS-MCT as coupler.

Resolution: 16 km (TL1279) for the atmosphere coupled to a 1/12 degree (~8 km) ocean model.

I/O: We define two different configurations, covering two use cases that are typical for simulations:

- **Climate studies and model tuning exercises:** Monthly output of u, v, w, T, P, specific humidity, cloud water and ice (all in 3D) and a number of 2D fields for the atmosphere will be saved. For the ocean, monthly output for u, v, w, T and salinity will be saved, as well as 2D fields.
- **High-end scenario:** 3hourly output for the main 3d fields in atmosphere and ocean as well as ~20 2d fields that are saved hourly and three fields on four pressure levels. This configuration will be used in the scalability exercises.

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond/dyiamond-2nd-phase-the-winter-experimental-protocol/view>

ICON-ESM:

We will use the coupled ICON-ESM model, which uses YAC as coupler. For scalability tests, we will use the same model configuration as used for the 2nd Phase of DYAMOND including the model I/O that is requested from the DYAMOND protocol (except for the use of hourly output (instead of 15-min) for 2D and pressure level fields). Depending on developments at MPI-M, we will include the ocean biogeochemistry model HAMOCC. On the Pre-Exascale systems we will perform ensemble simulations.

Resolution: 5 km (R2B9) for the atmosphere and 5 km (R2B9) for the ocean model.

I/O: Atmosphere: 3-hourly 3D output of u, v, w, T, P, specific humidity, cloud water and ice. Hourly output for ~20 fields in 2D as well as relative humidity, u and v on pressure levels (200, 500, 700 and 850 hPa). **Ocean:** 3-hourly output for u, v, w, T and salinity in the top 200m, daily output of full-depth 3D fields, as well as hourly output of 2D fields. Possibly additional output for OBGc tracers (3D top 200m fields on 3-hourly basis, 3D full-depth fields on daily basis, 2D fields on hourly basis)

ECMWF:

We will use the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) for the atmosphere coupled to the NEMO ocean model and the WAM wave model using an in-house coupling infrastructure. For scalability tests, we will use the same model configuration as used for the 2nd Phase of DYAMOND including the model I/O that is requested from the DYAMOND protocol (except for the use of hourly output for 2D and pressure level fields).

Resolution: 4 km (TCo2559) for the atmosphere coupled to a ¼ degree (25 km) ocean model.

I/O: Atmosphere: 3-hourly 3D output of u, v, w, T, P, specific humidity, cloud water and ice. Hourly output for ~20 fields in 2D as well as relative humidity, u and v on pressure levels (200, 500, 700 and 850 hPa). **Ocean:** 3-hourly output for u, v, w, T and salinity as well as hourly output of 2D fields.

IPSL-CM:

We will use the DYNAMICO atmosphere model coupled to the NEMO ocean model using the OASIS coupler. For scalability tests, we will use the model I/O as requested for the 2nd Phase of DYAMOND (except for the use of hourly output for 2D and pressure level fields).

Resolution: 10 km for the atmosphere coupled to a 1/12 degree (~8 km) ocean.

I/O: Atmosphere: 3-hourly 3D output of u, v, w, T, P, specific humidity, cloud water and ice. Hourly output for ~20 fields in 2D as well as relative humidity, u and v on pressure levels (200, 500, 700 and 850 hPa). **Ocean:** 3-hourly output for u, v, w, T and salinity as well as hourly output of 2D fields.